

Antimicrobial Effect of Essential Oil of Plant *Schinus molle* on Some Bacteria Pathogens

Authors : Mehani Mouna, Ladjel segni

Abstract : Humans use plants for thousands of years to treat various ailments, In many developing countries, Much of the population relies on traditional doctors and their collections of medicinal plants to cure them. Essential oils have many therapeutic properties. In herbal medicine, They are used for their antiseptic properties against infectious diseases of fungal origin, Against dermatophytes, Those of bacterial origin. The aim of our study is to determine the antimicrobial effect of essential oils of the plant *Schinus molle* on some pathogenic bacteria. It is a medicinal plant used in traditional therapy. Essential oils have many therapeutic properties. In herbal medicine, They are used for their antiseptic properties against infectious diseases of fungal origin, Against dermatophytes, Those of bacterial origin. The test adopted is based on the diffusion method on solid medium (Antibiogram), This method allows to determine the susceptibility or resistance of an organism according to the sample studied. Our study reveals that the essential oil of the plant *Schinus molle* has a different effect on the resistance of germs: For *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* strain is a moderately sensitive with an inhibition zone of 10 mm, Further Antirobactere, *Escherichia coli* and *Proteus* are strains that represent a high sensitivity, A zone of inhibition equal to 14.66 mm.

Keywords : Essential oil, microorganism, antibiogram, *shinus molle*

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